

1 TLR7 and TLR8 message quantity is regulated.

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7 Regulation of message quantity implies its functional control by limiting message number; TLR7 senses
8 nucleic acid in endosomes with TLR8, and dysfunction or impairment of these sensors is described as a
9 mechanistic basis of the autoimmune inflammatory disease system SLE, known commonly as lupus. The
10 data here involving NOD2 perturbations in human cells permitted disclosure of TLR8 control by NOD2 with
11 TLR8 loss as a major transcriptional difference globally, and TLR7 as a component of a regulatory system
12 as a system composed of genes whose message number is regulated and whose regulation is made
13 obvious by transcriptome comparison that reveals message number that is maintained without change and
14 at specific quantities (between 5 and 25 units) between cellular setting. SLE clinical presentation has a
15 known sex bias affecting females more frequently, and TLR7 and TLR8 mutation is described in SLE
16 literature. TLR7 and TLR8 message quantity may be controlled by Xist. Thus, Xist has more specific
17 functions (separate from prevention of genomic instability through counting based regulation of upper and
18 lower transcriptional thresholds) that are relevant for specific purposes like safeguarding toleragenic
19 responses and supporting integrity of the immune system through regulating quantities of machinery that
20 have useful roles in detection of non-self but whose aberrant function may also predispose to pathology
21 with prejudice, like TLR7 and TLR8.

22 Citations

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24 1. Jurk, M., Heil, F., Vollmer, J., Schetter, C., Krieg, A.M., Wagner, H., Lipford, G. and Bauer, S.,
25 2002. Human TLR7 or TLR8 independently confer responsiveness to the antiviral compound R-848.
26 Nature immunology, 3(6), pp.499-499.
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